

ETHICAL ISSUES IN THE INDIAN FINANCIAL SERVICES INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

The issue of ethics and economic efficiency in the provisioning and delivery of services becomes complex in the Indian context. Ethical issues in the financial services industry affect everyone, because even if you don't work in the field, you're a consumer of the services. Financial service industry encompasses banks, securities firms, insurance companies, mutual fund organizations, investment banks, pensions funds, mortgage lenders—any company doing business in the financial arena. Because of its vast size, the industry tends to garner lots of headlines, many of which tout its ethical lapses. This paper will try to look at the ethical aspects of the financial service industry towards stakeholders. An attempt of identifying few ethical issues relating Indian financial sector is made in this article.

Key words: Ethical issues, Financial services, Moral behaviour, Legal behaviour, Scams

Introduction: Financial intermediaries must keep to rules of law, industry standards and act ethically. Dealt with is ethical. What does it mean to act ethical in financial services? Law and industry standards are straightforward ethics an area for more interpretation. What is considered ethical in financial services? Ethics towards the customer,(investor or corporation looking for capital)?. Ethics towards the employer/employee and ethics towards the society?

Objectives:

The major objective of this research paper is to identify few ethical issues affecting Indian financial service industry and identify solutions for the same.

Research method:

The research is completely based on secondary data.

The issue of ethics and economic efficiency in the provisioning and delivery of services becomes complex in the Indian context. Ethical issues in the financial services industry affect everyone, because even if you don't work in the field, you're a consumer of the services. The public seems to have the perception that the financial services sector is more unethical than other areas of business. This misperception persists for several reasons. First of all, the industry itself is quite large. It encompasses banks, securities firms, insurance companies, mutual fund organizations, investment banks, pensions funds, mortgage lenders—any company doing business in the financial arena. Because of its vast size, the industry tends to garner lots of headlines, many of which tout its ethical lapses.

India's services sector has always served the Indian economy well, accounting for nearly 57 per cent of the gross domestic product (GDP). Here, the financial services segment has been a significant contributor.

The financial services sector in India is dominated by commercial banks which have more than 60 per cent share of the total assets; other segments include mutual funds, insurance firms, non-banking institutions, cooperatives and pension funds.

The Government of India has introduced reforms to liberalize, regulate and enhance the country's financial services industry. Presently, the country can claim to be one of the world's most vibrant capital markets. In spite of the challenges that are still there, the sector's future looks good.

Present financial system in India:

The present situation of Indian financial service sector could be broadly represented as follows;

- RBI, at the Apex
- Commercial banks which includes public sector and private sector Banks,
- Development financial institutions which could be divided into all India institutions and state level institutions,
- Insurance companies, which can be classified as, Life Insurance Corporation of India, General Insurance Corporation of India, and private sector insurance companies,
- Other public sector financial institutions like Post Office Savings bank, National housing bank, Export Import bank of India etc.
- Mutual funds
- Non Banking Finance Corporations
- Asset reconstruction companies
- Capital market intermediaries,
- Credit information companies.

Market Size:

The size of banking assets in India reached US\$ 1.8 trillion in FY 13 and is projected to touch US\$ 28.5 trillion by FY 25.

Information technology (IT) services, the largest spending segment of India's insurance industry at Rs 4,000 crore (US\$ 665.78 million) in 2014, is anticipated to continue enjoying strong growth at 16 per cent. Category leaders are business process outsourcing (BPO) at 25 per cent and consulting at 21 per cent. (<http://www.ibef.org/industry/financial-services-india.aspx>, 7TH September 12pm)

The industry is also highly regulated, so it's likely that a higher percentage of these bad transactions are identified and reported, perhaps more so than in other less regulated industries. But ethical lapses do occur, and we have discussed five reasons why these misdeeds may happen.

In Keynote address by Dr Duvvuri Subbarao, the then Governor of the Reserve Bank of India, at the Conference on "Ethics and the World of Finance", organised by Sri Sathya Sai University, Prasanthi Nilayam, Andhra Pradesh, 28 August 2009 said that the difference between the financial sector and other businesses is therefore quite clear. If say, a soap manufacturing company is an astounding success, who benefits? The shareholders and the management. And if it fails, who loses? Both of the above. But in the case of a bank, the story is different. If the bank is a success, who benefits? The shareholders and the management. And if it fails, who loses? Not the shareholders and the management, but the public at whose expense the bank is bailed out. The ripple effect is less pronounced but similar in the case of all institutions in the financial sector even if they are not banks.

That crucial difference, I believe, underscores the special ethical dimension of the financial sector in contrast to other businesses. Banks and financial institutions have a greater responsibility of being conscious of the obligation they have of not jeopardizing the larger public interest. What Mahatma Gandhi said, that businesses hold public money in trust, is more true of the financial sector than others. (BIS Review 103/2009)

Major Financial Scams in India:

Security scams and financial scandals have led to the manipulation of large amount of money, bloating stock markets and sensex. Even the financial markets having regulatory authority and empowered legal sections have failed in providing good corporate governance to some extent.

2G Spectrum Scam:

Former Telecom Minister A. Raja is the prime accused who is considered to be the mastermind in this scam by CBI. He stands accused of under-valuing spectrum as the country's Telecom Minister and selling it to companies he favored, though they were largely ineligible for licenses to run mobile networks. The loss to the national exchequer is pegged by the government auditor at a mind-boggling Rs. 1.76 lakh crore.

Satyam Case:

Mr. Ramalinga Raju, the former Chairman and Chief Executive of Satyam Computer Services admitted to falsification in the company accounts and various other irregularities. The estimated fraud was Rs.700 Crore billion. Coming on the back of global recession, this incident busts the Indian Outsourcing Industry and the stock market.

IPO Scam: A number of key operators, including corporate stock brokers such as Karvy and Indiabulls, were involved in the IPO scam during 2004-05. The modus operandi of the scam was that the operators opened thousands of fake accounts to purchase shares in IPOs in the hope of selling later at huge profits. A spate of IPOs issued during this period was heavily oversubscribed due to this scam. Roopalben Panchal of IndiaBulls Securities is allegedly the mastermind of the scam. The Income-Tax Department in Ahmedabad has found that two major accused, Panchal and Sugandh Investments, have together made Rs 60.62 crore in 18 months.

DSQ Software Scam: Mr.Dinesh Dalmia, Managing Director of DSQ Software was accused of dubious acquisitions and biased allotment in the year 2000 and 2001.The amount involved in the Scam was Rs.595 Crores.

Telgi Scam: Abdul Karim Telgi mastered the art of forgery in printing duplicate stamp papers and sold them to banks and other institutions. He paid bribes to get access to the security press in Nasik, where stamp papers and currency notes are printed. He later used this knowledge to print fake stamp papers. Telgi's network spanned 14 states, 125 banks and more than 1000 employees. The Telgi clearly had a lot of support from government departments that were responsible for the production and sale of high security stamps. The extent of this scam was estimated to be about 200 crores.

Minorities Finance Corporation scam – Cheques issued to 16 fake companies

Tuesday, 16 October 2012 - Hyderabad, October 16: (Siasat News) Court has to decide about the police custody of four accused persons said to be involved in Minorities Finance Corporation scam. They are Sai Kumar, Managing Director of 'One Nation One Card', his companion Venkataraman, Keshava Rao (Middleman between Finance Corporation and bank), Navin Sagar (Assistant Manager of Vijaya Bank). Investigations made by C.I.D. have revealed some startling information. Sai Kumar opened a current account bearing number 40013003011000242 in Kothi and Nallakunta branches of Vijaya Bank. Although it was difficult task but Assistant Manager of Vijaya Bank, Navin Sagar helped him. He got issued Rs. 55,47,580 in favour of 16 fake companies. C.I.D. found that Keshava Rao got Rs. 68 and Rs. 10 crore deposited in the fixed deposit accounts of Nallakunta, Bandlaguda and Kothi branches of Vijaya Bank.

Odisha Chit Fund Scam: CBI to Probe 44 Companies

At least chit fund companies operating in Odisha, have come under the CBI scanner. The Supreme Court has ordered a CBI probe into the multi-crore chit fund scam, involving Saradha Group of Companies in West Bengal and 43 others operating in Odisha and beyond.

(<http://breakingnewsonline.in/odisha/1645-odisha-chit-fund-scam-cbi-to-probe-43-companies>)

Those are the few scams which happened only due to various ethical problems or issue. This study has identified the following five issues influencing such scams.

1) Self-interest sometimes morphs into greed and selfishness, which is unchecked self-interest at the expense of someone else. This greed becomes a kind of accumulation fever. If you accumulate for the sake of accumulation, accumulation becomes the end, and if accumulation is the end, there's no place to stop. The focus shifts from the long-term to the short-term, with a big emphasis on profit maximization.

For example, swaps (where two communication companies agree to exchange the right to use excess bandwidth on their networks) fall into this category. Each company recognizes the income generated in the quarter earned and defers the expenses through capitalizing them as an asset and logging the cost as a recognized expense over time, resulting in an inflated bottom line. Companies may make money out of their finance department—not from selling products, not from doing what the company did, not from fulfilling the company's mission, but from playing around with its asset mix.

2) Some people suffer from stunted moral development: This happens in three areas: the failure to be taught, the failure to look beyond one's own perspective, and the lack of proper mentoring.

Business schools too often reduce everything to an economic entity. They do this by saying the fundamental purpose of a business is to make money, maximize profit, or the really jazzy words 'maximize shareholder value,' or something like that. And it never gets questioned. If the fundamental purpose never gets questioned, the ethics never get questioned, because the fundamental purpose of something gives you the reason for its existence. It tells you whether you're doing it well or not. It's the ultimate ethical question: What's your purpose?

3) Some people equate moral behavior with legal behavior, disregarding the fact that even though an action may not be illegal, it still may not be moral. Everyone must remember that the reason for all laws is that the moral agreement begins to break down, and the way to get other people in line is to legislate so that we can stipulate punishments. Yet some people contend that the only requirement is to obey the law. They tend to ignore the spirit of the law in only following the letter of the law.

For example, Companies Act, Contract Laws etc, regulations repeatedly single out actions with “no legitimate business purpose” (like swaps.) If you are doing things with no legitimate business purpose in order to avoid taxation, what are you doing? You’re violating the spirit, are you not? You’re staying within the letter, but there’s no purpose there except to get you around the law.

4) Professional duty can conflict with company demands. For example, a faulty reward system can induce unethical behavior. A purely self-interested agent would choose that course of action which contains the highest returns to him or herself.

For example, consider the misguided practice of selling indexed annuities to the elderly. If a company is paying a high commission for that product, say 15 percent, versus a lower commission for a more appropriate product, say 3 percent, a salesperson may disregard the needs of the client and/or assume that the company supports this product and its applicability by its willingness to pay fivefold the compensation. Sooner or later, people are going to give in to that temptation. The purely self-interested agent is just responding to the reward system that is in place. “You need to take a look at what you are rewarding.” In general, organizations get exactly what they reward. They just don’t realize that their rewards structures are encouraging dysfunctional or counter-productive behavior or turn a blind eye to the outcome.

5) Individual responsibility can wither under the demands of the client. Sometimes the push to act unethically comes from the client. How many people expect their accountants to pad their expenses where possible? How many clients expect their insurance agents to falsify their applications or claims? “That’s the temptation—you like

your client, you've gotten to know your client, you really want to help your client out—that's just another conflicting loyalty," Duska said.

It is quite natural and acceptable that people who do business are, for the most part, highly ethical people trying to do the right thing most of the time. Most of them are trying to help their clients achieve their financial objectives. But how could this be better, because clearly, even if I'm right, there are still a lot of issues and problems in the business?

Suggestions:

First of all, consumers need to be better informed. It is customer's responsibility to take control of their own financial security, which doesn't mean one need to know everything about the product he/she is buying in advance, but he/she should read enough to know what some of the right questions are to ask. Ask those insightful questions of an advisor whom you know, trust, and who has the proper credentials, if applicable.

Other suggestions:

- Incentive compensation better aligned with customers' interests, rather than agents'
- More industry trade associations supporting ethics initiatives
- The Center for Ethics in Financial Services growing in influence and impact
- Internal and external audit and a compliance department/compliance officer are needed to avoid fraud and other unwanted unethical behavior.
- Conflict of interest should if possible be avoided
- Market manipulation should be curbed.

Conclusion: As we all have read, there is an opinion that greed and unethical behavior by market participants is a culprit for financial crises and therefore it would be unwise to ignore the area of ethics and the requirements ethics put on market participants. Financial intermediaries must keep to rules of law, industry standards and act ethically. Dealing

with ethics is not a sideline of the financial service industry but should be a part of its core. It could be properly said that financial service industry must have absolute ethical standards.

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